

From the teaching centres

Psychiatry and homoeopathy

Basis for a dialogue

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Abstract

A comparison is made between psychiatry and homoeopathy, with reference to five homoeopathic principles. These are the law of similars, the self-healing principle, the microdose effect, Hering's Law and diagnosis through pattern recognition. There is evidence that all of these have been incorporated into contemporary psychiatry, and that recent neurobiological research provides a measure of validation to these age-old teachings. Some testable research questions are also proposed.

KEY WORDS: Psychiatry; Homoeopathy; Law of similars; Self-healing; Micro-dose; Hering's Law; Rollback; Pattern recognition.

Introduction

As a system of therapeutics, homoeopathy has withstood the test of time and is now enjoying a modest resurgence of interest.^{1,2} However, homoeopathy remains poorly understood by most of the medical profession, who are still all too ready to dismiss it, or even to bring about its demise, as exemplified by recent events in the state of North Carolina.

There are a number of reasons why the entire medical profession should at least take a serious look at homoeopathy, even if they choose to not to adopt it in their own practice.

—There is now good evidence from credible investigators that homoeopathy is a therapeutically active system, superior to placebo effects in a wide range of conditions.²

—Secondly, it is one of the underlying premises of homoeopathy that this form of treatment engages the body's self-healing system, which should mean that successful homoeopathy will lead to cure in a large number of cases.

—The medication is generally free of serious side effects.

—Homoeopathic medicines are usually inexpensive.

One way to achieve a rapprochement

between conventional medicine ('allopathy') and homoeopathy is to evaluate the degree to which there may be points in common between the two systems. There are a number of striking similarities between psychiatry and homoeopathy, with recent neurobiological research tending to validate some age-old homoeopathic precepts. It is the purpose of this review to draw attention to parallels between the two disciplines, focusing on the law of similars, the self-healing principle, the microdose effect, disappearance of symptoms in reverse order to that of their appearance, and diagnosis by pattern recognition rather than aetiology. These are all summarized in Table 1. A number of testable hypotheses and research questions are also advanced.

Law of similars

A central tenet of homoeopathy is that like is cured by like. According to this postulate, the most effective treatment for a given clinical constellation is one which can induce the same symptom picture when given at higher doses, either to healthy or diseased individuals. Traditional depth psychotherapies, as well as the more recently developed cognitive and behavioural treatments for anxiety disorder,

TABLE 1. *Points of similarity between psychiatry and homoeopathy*

	<i>Psychiatry</i>	<i>Homoeopathy</i>
<i>Therapeutic principle</i>	1) Evoking the symptom in controlled way during psychotherapy 2) Some somatic treatments induce the symptom	Therapy follows Law of Similars
<i>Self-healing principle</i>	Some symptoms may reflect on endogenous self-corrective principle	Vital force
<i>Microdose effect</i>	Time dependent sensitization	Serial dilutions and succussions
<i>Sequencing of symptoms</i>	Rollback	Hering's Law
<i>Diagnostic Process</i>	Non-aetiological; pattern recognition	Total symptom and clinical picture

all share in common a similar therapeutic principle, namely that in order to cure the symptoms successfully, the treatment itself is either capable of evoking, or actually does evoke, these symptoms in a controlled manner. Thus, exposure therapy for panic attacks, phobic anxiety and obsessive compulsive disorder evokes symptoms, rather than suppresses them.^{3,4} Put differently, the therapy that works is the therapy that induces symptoms of the disorder.

A good example of a treatment which induces the symptoms from which the patient wants relief is the Panic Control Treatment (PCT) developed by Barlow.⁵ This treatment programme for panic disorder is based on systematic structured exposure to feared internal sensations. If palpitations are a major symptom, then exercise will be used to evoke these. Respiratory symptoms, if a leading problem, can be activated by hyperventilation. Repeated in-session and between-session exposures are prescribed in PCT, which is more effective than placebo treatment, and as effective as alprazolam, a benzodiazepine drug. Another example is the use of paradoxical intention in Frankl's logotherapy,⁶ a technique which directs the patient to do the thing that is feared.

More recent biological research also provides an example of this principle in that sleep deprivation can be used successfully in the short term to treat depression, a disorder in which sleep loss is one of the cardinal symptoms.⁷ In sleep deprivation, the patient is either kept awake all night or awoken at a certain time and not allowed to return to sleep.

The self-healing principle

Homoeopathy teaches that symptoms represent the body's effort at restoration of health

in the face of a pathogenic influence.⁸ Recent neurobiological research by Post and Weiss⁹ has advanced a similar view, that some symptoms of major affective disorder can also be, as they put it, 'good guys', in that they may reflect the body's self-treating activity rather than the disease process itself. Post and Weiss state that data suggest that some alterations occur in the affective disorders which may be compensatory and adaptive, i.e. part of an endogenous therapeutic mechanism rather than the primary pathology. They provide supportive evidence from studies of the hypothalamo-pituitary-thyroid axis in depression, and extend their reasoning to seizure disorders as well. Examples might include the fact that insomnia could be an endogenous 'therapeutic' process, rather than primary pathology, in depression, since induction of total insomnia produces mood improvement. Elevated TRH levels, found in patients with kindled seizures, exert anticonvulsant effects and could be the body's compensatory response at restoring homeostasis.

Since TRH elevations are also found in depression, perhaps the same could be true in this disorder. Post and Weiss state that one clear implication is the development of therapeutic strategies which promote endogenous self-correcting processes. Homoeopathy is one such approach: indeed, this is what homoeopathy claims to be all about. These observations of a possible self-healing process in depression are compatible with the homoeopathic notion of a vital force, endowed with the ability to change in response to altered circumstances and which is directed at the rebuilding of a damaged organism.¹⁰

A further question arises in that, if some of

the symptoms and physico-chemical changes in affective disorders reflect an endogenous compensatory mechanism, could it be that most, or perhaps all, symptoms may be so conceived?

How might we tell which are therapeutic and which are pathogenic? It would be fruitful to study homeopathy in affective disorder, and to explore what effects this treatment would have on neurobiological parameters. There is at least one case report¹¹ suggesting that homeopathy can ameliorate severe cycling bipolar disorder, and that the milder mixed anxiety depressive states may also respond to homeopathy.¹²

Microdose effect

One of the major stumbling blocks in the way of accepting homeopathy is the microdose phenomenon, i.e. the belief that therapeutic efficacy remains after serial dilutions to ultramolecular levels beyond Avogadro's number.¹³ While psychiatric research has not tackled the microdose phenomenon as such, recent work by Antelman¹⁴ suggests that this is not such a far-fetched idea. Antelman describes the model of time-dependent sensitization (TDS) as an explanation for the effects of psychotropic drugs. Sensitization refers to the ability of a potentially threatening stimulus (e.g. a drug) to induce a response which can later on be elicited, or even amplified, by exposure to a similar or weaker agent. Key determinants of TDS are 1) the potentially threatening nature of the original stimulus; 2) its intermittent administration; 3) the ability of time to induce sensitization, sometimes even in the absence of repeated exposure. Perhaps we are all somewhat guilty of the medical crime of 'therapeutic furore'. In our haste to 'do' something, we may not allow time a chance with more minimalistic therapeutic action.

TDS may be a useful concept in understanding treatment of psychiatric disorders. Single doses of drugs or their occasional intermittent use, are capable of eliciting profound and persistent responses in animals and humans. These responses last long after the disappearance of drug from the body. In one therapeutic trial of clomipramine in depression,¹⁵ two intravenous doses resulted in a marked antidepressant effect long after the drug had disappeared, and was not measurable in plasma. While it could be argued that

the initial dose was certainly not ultramolecular, the fact remains that a small loading dose was sufficient to set in place a progressive decline in levels of depression at the same time that the drug was disappearing from the system, a concept which is at variance with current clinical psychopharmacological thinking. If major depression can respond to two single doses of a drug, is it too fanciful to presume that it could also respond to the right medicine given as a microdose? The TDS process implies that very small doses can evoke a certain set of responses, that time itself is an important vector as we think about physico-chemical change after even a single dose of drug, and that in some instances time itself can produce later changes without repetition of drug dose or stimulus. However, while having some features in common with the microdose effect, TDS does not in any way relate to the process of succussion, without which serial dilution to microdoses is unlikely to be effective.

Hering's Law and rollback

Hering noted that symptoms tended to remit in the reverse order of their appearance.¹⁶ Recent symptoms may be first to disappear and chronologically earlier symptoms may temporarily reappear during recovery. These may or may not call for treatment. Some would avoid their suppression on the grounds that to do so would interfere with the healing process. In contemporary psychiatry, it is my belief that we no longer pay very much attention to the sequencing of symptom appearance or disappearance, generally being in a hurry to remove troublesome symptoms as quickly as possible. However, the exact counterpart to Hering's law has been described by Detre and Jarecki,¹⁷ who refer to the rollback phenomenon in affective disorder.

Rollback can be either temporal or symptomatic. Temporal rollback refers to the time taken for an illness to remit, which corresponds to the time taken for it to unfold. Symptomatic rollback refers to the fact that symptoms of depression disappear in the reverse order of their arising. Renewed attention given to such concepts by psychiatrists today may help achieve a better understanding of disease phenomenology, prognosis and treatment principles. Homeopathy never lost sight of these.

Pattern recognition

Homeopathic prescribing is based on the total clinical picture; the symptom is not seen

merely as reflecting a presumed underlying aetiopathology which needs to be identified and treated. The total clinical picture corresponds to a pattern of symptoms, signs, constitutional factors, behaviours, emotions, attitudes, tastes and modalities.¹⁸ Within the pattern, differential weighting may be given to component parts. The physician's task is to recognize the particular patient's pattern and choose the medicine accordingly. Although psychiatry aspires to the aetiopathological model, it still continues to be very much a pattern-based activity. The *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM 3R)* of the American Psychiatric Association is almost entirely an assemblage of 'patterns', with very few disorders being framed aetiologically or pathogenically. To take the analogy even further, certain constitutional and enduring personality variables have now become incorporated into the process of treatment selection. For example, the pyknic body type is a positive outcome predictor for electroconvulsive therapy, while hysterical personality traits are negative predictors for this treatment.¹⁹ Exaggerated tendencies to show rejection sensitivity as a premorbid trait are related to positive effects for MAO inhibitors.²⁰ Thus the good psychiatrist, like the good homoeopath, will acknowledge the importance of the 'total clinical picture', i.e. the overall pattern, in selection of treatment. One remaining important problem for both homoeopathy and psychiatry is the inadequately tested reliability among raters as to whether or not they agree upon pattern recognition.²¹ This would seem to be an important area for research in homoeopathic practice.

Patterns have the potential to be infinitely complex or they may be quite simple. They have been construed as the external representation of form-creating fields.²² Jungian psychology refers to archetypal fields which can give rise to psychic structures ('patterns'), which may also have counterparts in the external world, through the 'principle of synchronicity'.²³

Archetypes are not restricted to the world of psychology, but the concept has a broader application to include the world of disease as well. In that case, we may surmise that archetypal fields give rise to a vast number of disease patterns, and that the same pattern exists within the organism and in the outer world, as embodied in the *similimum*, or the

'synchronistic' treatment. By finding the appropriate *similimum* which matches the disease pattern, the organism can be made whole again. This is tantamount to a form of physical individuation, using terminology developed by Jung with regard to the process of psychological growth or attaining wholeness. In this sense, one may view homoeopathy as a form of pharmacological individuation.

Some testable questions

This review suggests the need to test out a number of clinical psychiatric questions. Some of them could be tested quite easily, given resolve and resources. Others would be more ambitious, but at least bear to be stated as theoretically important.

Does homoeopathy produce health or remove disease?

Treatment can either remove disease/symptoms or improve feelings of well-being, or both. It is possible to feel better about one's self or the quality of one's life even if the disease has not been cured. Clinical trials of homoeopathic treatment in psychiatric illness can be designed to evaluate both the quality of life and symptom intensity. Studies with conventional antidepressants have shown that symptom improvement tends to occur earlier than the patient's ability to return to productive work, and that the two processes are to some degree independent.²⁴ How might homoeopathy fare in this regard?

Does homoeopathy produce cure?

According to the self healing hypothesis, if homoeopathy successfully engages this process then there should be no appreciable relapse once the medication is stopped. Since relapse is a major problem following discontinuation of antidepressants and anxiolytics, clinical trials of homoeopathy should build in a follow-up period. Furthermore, the question should be asked about the length of homoeopathic treatment for acute and chronic psychiatric disorder: what is a minimal duration, and for which particular conditions? How is the dose selected?

What is the effect of combined homoeopathic and allopathic treatment?

Many clients are already receiving antidepressants and anxiolytic drugs, and may be reluc-

tant to give these up. There are also problems associated with the discontinuation of some anxiolytic agents. Is homoeopathy still effective in combination with allopathic antidepressant and anxiolytic drugs? Are the dose requirements different? Systematic clinical trials are needed to answer this question.

Controlled trials

There is only one known controlled trial of a homoeopathic and an allopathic psychotropic drug, and that was an open study.¹² There is a compelling need to undertake double blind clinical trials which evaluate homoeopathy, placebo and standard treatments in the everyday psychiatric diseases such as depression and anxiety. The trial methodology should incorporate currently acceptable study design, while accommodating to the special needs of homoeopathy (e.g. individualized assignment to treatment).

Homoeopathy as preventive treatment

Evaluation of mental, emotional and temperament-related characteristics is an essential part of medicine selection in homoeopathy. There is growing evidence that a number of affective and anxiety disorders arise in the context of certain temperaments.^{25, 26} In principle, there should be reason to expect that early administration of well-chosen homoeopathic medicines could prevent the emergence of more pathological or distressing manifestations of depression, mania or fear in susceptible people. Homoeopathic medicines may be comparable to lithium in this sense. There are far-reaching implications to this proposal, which would be difficult to test, but nonetheless very important.

Are more provings needed?

Late-20th-century psychiatry differs significantly from its early-20th-century counterpart. New diseases have arisen, old ones declined. It is quite possible that diseases go through phenomenological change across generations, i.e. there is a cohort effect. Our understanding of psychiatric phenomenology has changed considerably, especially with regard to non-psychotic disorders such as anxiety, traumatic stress, depression, eating disorders, sexual disorders and reactions to violence and abuse. One may question whether the old 19th-century repertories do adequate justice to late-20th-century psychi-

atry. It has been said that provings with potentized substances elicit very fine differentiation with respect to emotional and mental characteristics.²⁷ Perhaps a new round of provings is needed to which new psychiatric insights can be applied. Of particular importance, as a general comment on all provings, is the need to employ a double-blind placebo control, to clarify whether, in fact, the claimed effects of a substance are due to the substance. Provings are the homoeopathic equivalent of Phase 1 studies in conventional clinical pharmacology trials of new allopathic compounds.

Conclusion

In summary, there are a number of important similarities between psychiatry and homoeopathy, which can, in part, be taken as validating some of the homoeopathic tenets. They also suggest that psychiatry and homoeopathy can become engaged in profitable collaboration and that, by bringing to bear recent medical technology, we may learn more about the mechanism of how homoeopathy works, how mental illnesses arise and also about the recovery process.

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